

FACTORS AFFECTING BEHAVIORAL INTENTION TOWARDS E-WALLET—A CASE STUDY AMONG FOUNDATION STUDENTS

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 8 Sept 2023 Revised: Nov 20, 2023 Accepted: 27 Feb 2024 Published: 1 April 2024</p>	<p>E-Wallet is an electronic financial transaction made online via mobile devices. The development of technologies has promoted the higher usage of this method among users around the world. This study aims to investigate the factors affecting behavioral intention among Foundation Studies students towards the usage of E-Wallet. There are 150 students involved in this study. Descriptive statistics were adopted to achieve the research objective. The finding shows that 87% of the respondents preferred to used e-wallets in their daily life activities and majority of them are female students. Students from urban area are more familiar with the E-Wallet and promotion of the benefits of E-Wallet should be conducted in the rural area.</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Due to the rapid advancement of technology in the 21st century, the use of E-Wallet has grown in popularity in our society. E-Wallet is a software that helps us to store money online and allows us to perform online transactions through our devices, whether they are a smartphone, tablet, or computer. There are numerous types of electronic wallets that we can use daily (Chauhan, Shingari & Shingari, 2017; Abushamleh, Al-Hiyari & Qusef, 2021; Singh, 2019). For instance, GrabPay, Boost, BigPay, KiplePay, Touch n Go, QRPay to name a few. Users can access their E-Wallet at any time by downloading the mobile application, starting their first payment, and enjoying the services available for the users (Teng & Khong, 2021; Ying & Mohamed, 2020).

Furthermore, some features let users link their E-Wallet with their active bank account. This allows them to deposit their money from the respective bank account into their E-Wallet smoothly. In addition, E-Wallet also has an auto-reload feature which will automatically reload the money for the users when their balance falls below the limit they set earlier. By enabling this feature, users can make sure that they have sufficient balance at any time they want to use their E-Wallet.

However, not everyone agrees that using an E-Wallet to make payments is a convenient option due to security issues and efficiency concerned. Some think that paying with cash physically is easier and more reliable than paying through E-Wallet. With an increase in news of hacking events, ransomware attacks, data leaks, and other security breaches, consumers/users becoming increasingly skeptical about transferring their financial information online.

Therefore, in this study, a sample survey was conducted among students in the Foundation Studies to learn more about their attitudes towards the usage of E-Wallet. In conclusion, it is hoped that the outcome from this study can help the users to gain a better understanding and summaries on what causes the students to use E-Wallet and encourage the non-E-Wallet users among the respondents to use them in the future.

Thus, the objectives of this research are to analyze respondents' personal and family background and their interest in using E-Wallet, to investigate the level of satisfaction of the respondents about the usage of E-Wallet, to measure the amount spent by the respondents per month on E-Wallet and to determine the most popular E-Wallet platform among the respondents.

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in descriptive nature. The factors affecting behavioral intentions to use E-Wallet among the students who are currently pursuing Foundation Studies in Management at one of the higher education institute in Malaysia were investigated. Primary data was collected for the investigation. Feedback directly from the Foundation Studies students was gathered through a set of questionnaires (Bhandari, 2021). The set of questionnaires was developed through Google form which was then passed to the students via online platform.

150 students of Foundation Studies were volunteered to spend their valuable time in responding to the questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 25 questions in total. 10 questions were about respondent's personal information and family background and the other 15 questions were prepared with scale range to measure their level of agreement on each statement. Scale 1 clearly indicates that the respondent strongly disagrees while scale 6 indicates that the respondent strongly agrees with the statement given.

The list of questions linked to factors that affecting behavioral intention of Foundation Studies students to use E-Wallet are as follows:

Factor 1: Convenience

1. I intend to use E-wallet because it is very convenient.
2. I do not get frustrated when I use E-wallet.
3. E-wallet is easy to learn and use.

4. I feel flexible in performing payment using E-wallet.
5. Less effort is needed when I perform payment using E-wallet.

Factor 2: Advantages Gained

6. I intend to use E-wallet because it provides a wide range of products.
7. I use E-wallet because I think it is beneficial to me (cashback, discount coupon, etc).
8. A wide variety of E-wallet providers ease my online shopping process.

Factor 3: Risk & Security Issues

9. Most E-wallet provides adequate payment security.
10. E-wallet has minimum financial risk.
11. I would assume E-wallet is safe as if security verified by third party.
12. I prefer to use E-wallet that provides security insurance.

Factor 4: Social & Peer Influence

13. I will only use an E-wallet system if I heard it before.
14. The comments from other people will influence my intention to use an E-wallet.
15. I will use an E-wallet when my friends introduce it to me.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Respondents Profile Analysis

Figure 1 shows the gender of 150 foundation students who participated in this study. The figure displays that 83% of the participants are female, which represents 125 female students, while 17% of the participants are male, which represents 25 male students.

Figure 1: Gender of Respondents

Figure 2: Race of the Respondents

Figure 2 displays the races of the students who responded to the survey. According to the figure, Malay is the major race, with 129 students forming 86% of the sample who answered the survey among all the races, which are Chinese, Indian, and others. The total number of Chinese students in Foundation Studies is 13, comprising 9% of the students. Indian and other race students are equal where there are four Indian students and four students belonging to other races, which represents 3% each.

The state of origin of the respondents is shown in Figure 3. From this figure, it can be seen that most of the Foundation Studies students are from Kedah, constituting 24% representing 36 students. In contrast, only 1 student comes from Sabah, constituting 0.67%.

Figure 3: Respondents State of Origin

Table 1: Respondents Hometown

	Hometown	Frequency	Percentage (%)
	Rural	61	40.67
	Urban	89	59.33
Total		150	100
Maximum		89	-
Minimum		61	-
Range		28	-
Mode	Urban		-

Table 1 shows the respondents hometown. There are 61 students which are from the rural area, with a percentage of 40.67%, while 59.33% which represent 89 students are from the urban area.

Figure 4: Respondents Family Income

According to Figure 4, there are 30 students that have a family income of less than or equal to RM2000 per month, while 35 students have a family income between RM2001 to RM4000. For a family income of RM4001 to RM6000, a total of 23 students belong to this category, while a family income of RM6001-RM8000 has a total of 13 students. In addition, 16 students have a family income of RM8001-RM10001, and 33 students have a family income of RM10001 and above.

Figure 5 shows the usage of E-Wallet daily among the students that involved in this study. There are 85% of students who use the E-Wallet and 15% of the students who didn't use the E-Wallet. 85% represents 127 students, while 15% represents 23 students.

Pie chart in Figure 6 shows the types of E-Wallet used by the 150 Foundation Studies students. From the pie chart, most of the students prefer to use Touch n Go application (42%), follow by QRpay by bank users (34%). Only 1% of the students use Grab Pay and Kiple Pay. The other 9% of students chose other applications and 13% did not used any type of E-Wallet.

Figure 5: Usage of E-Wallet in Daily Life

Figure 6: Type of E-Wallet Used

Figure 7 displays the amount of money students have spent on their E-Wallet in a month. As can be seen in the figure, 127 out of 150 students spent less than RM 200 on E-Wallet in a month. In addition, there are 16 students who spend below RM400 and 4 students who spend below RM600, but there is only 1 student who spends below RM800, and 2 students spend RM1000 on E-Wallet. The highest percentage of the data is 84.67%, which represents an amount of RM0 to RM199 being spent on E-Wallet.

Figure 7: Amount Spent on E-Wallet in a Month

Analysis on the Factors

Measuring E-Wallet Based on Convenience

From the data collected, level 1 of the agreement shows that the respondents strongly disagree, while level 6 shows that the respondents strongly agree with the statement. Figure 8 clearly shows that a lot of students agreed with the statement related to how the convenience factor affects Foundation Studies students behavioral intention to use E-Wallet. Although there were a few students who disagreed, majority of the students agreed that E-Wallet is super convenient for them to use by rating each statement at a high level of agreement, which were 5 and 6. Thus, this convenience factor is one of the major reasons why majority of the students used E-Wallet to make online payments.

Figure 8: Measuring E-Wallet Based on Convenience

Measuring E-Wallet Based on Advantages Gained Factor

Figure 9: Measuring E-Wallet Based on Advantages Gained Factor

Based on Figure 9, it can be observed that none of the respondents rated as strongly disagreed (level 1) with the statements of advantages gained as the factor influencing their behavior intention to use E-Wallet. Even though there are 2 to 3 respondents who still disagree, most of the respondents agree with the statements that using E-Wallet is very beneficial. This further proves that students can gain various benefits by using E-Wallet as their payment system.

Measuring E-Wallet Based on Risk and Security Issues

Figure 10: Measuring E-Wallet Based on Risk and Security Issues

From Figure 10, most of the respondents either agree or strongly agree that the E-Wallet system is safe to use as it provides adequate payment security, and nearly 50 students have a neutral agreement that E-Wallet has minimum financial risk. This prove that the current non-E-Wallet users can have faith and try using E-Wallet as their payment method.

Measuring E-Wallet Based on Social and Peer Influence

As displays in Figure 11, a very small number of respondents disagree that social and peer influence affect the students' attitudes towards E-Wallet. However, 1/3 of the respondents, a total of 50 students, strongly agree that the comments from others will influence their intention to use E-Wallet. Therefore, those E-wallet users who have gained many benefits and experienced good things using E-Wallet all the while should share their opinions with others and encourage them to consider using it as their payment method.

Figure 11: Measuring E-wallet Based on Social and Peer Influence

CONCLUSION

Based on the survey and analysis done on the respondent profile, it showed that 86.67% of 150 Foundation Studies students seem to prefer using E-Wallet while only 13.33% of the students reacted otherwise. Since the world is now revolving from time to time towards technology, a lot of businesses at the campus have started to come forward to use online payment to ease their students. However, network problems often occurred at the campus which cause the students to be worried about using online payment instead of paying physically that is using cash. The management of the higher institution should take relevant steps to overcome the network problem and ease the students' problem while making online payments. Thus, this is not a barrier to students using E-wallets in their daily lives in campus.

According to our survey, 42% of 150 students used Touch n Go E-Wallet while only 1% of the students use Kipple Pay. Meanwhile, most of the stores in the campus only accept online payment through Kipple Pay E-Wallet. This is not very convenient for majority of the students who mainly use Touch n Go as their main E-Wallet. Thus, shops with only the Kipple Pay option might face difficulties in making more sales and profits as the students would prefer shops with the Touch n Go option. It would be best if the Centre for Foundation Studies could encourage all the shops in campus to provide various types of E-Wallet options. This will make students feel more at ease when purchasing and paying for their items.

Moreover, it is observed that female students preferred using E-Wallet more than male students. This might be due to the fact that there are more female students in Foundation Studies than male students. 125 students out of the 150 respondents are female. Relating to this, preference of using E-Wallet more among female is due to another factor, which is their safety. In this modern era, it is getting more dangerous for female students to walk around carrying cash alone. From the current news we tend to see that women tend to be the primary victims when it comes to street robbery or theft. Therefore, it would be really helpful if all the shops in campus

to have the option for E-Wallet payment.

Finally, the survey also shows that students' hometowns can be an influencing factor on their preference for using E-Wallet. According to the data, students from rural areas have a lower preference for using E-Wallet to make online payments than students from urban areas. This is because most of businesses in urban areas accept E-Wallet payments. In addition, urban areas are more highly developed areas in the context of technology and infrastructure than rural areas. More explanation and promotion about the E-Wallet payment system and its benefits should be spread to the students especially for the students from rural areas. This may help to bring about a change in their perception and preference and make them feel more convinced to take step out from their comfort zone.

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